

Climate Change Journalism in the Zimbabwean Press: Some Empirical Reflections

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This qualitative study is an inquiry into the state of climate change journalism in Zimbabwe's main daily newspapers *The Herald* and *Daily News*. *The Herald* is a government-controlled newspaper while the *Daily News* is privately owned and does not suffer state interference in its operations. Guided by the sociology news production theory and the political economy of the media theory, the study seeks a nuanced understanding of the state of climate change reporting at the two selected newspapers. It therefore seeks to comprehend the challenges and prospects for this journalism genres in Zimbabwe. Data is gathered through in-depth interviews with purposively selected journalists at *The Herald* and *Daily News*. Findings suggest that two newspapers do not treat climate change seriously. The majority of the stories generated by the two newspapers are from press statements issued by government, or non-governmental organisations or are event-driven. This elitist approach to climate change journalism denies ordinary citizens a voice in fighting climate change.

Keywords: Climate change, *The Herald*, *Daily News*, Zimbabwe, patriotic journalism, oppositional journalism

The study examines the state of climate change journalism in the Zimbabwean press. It is a comparative analysis of two daily newspapers - the state-controlled newspaper *The Herald* and the privately-owned *Daily News*. These newspapers ride on distinct editorial policies. Published by Zimbabwe Newspapers (1980) Private Limited (Zimpapers), *The Herald's* editorial disposition reflects government thinking on crucial issues affecting Zimbabwe and achieves this through its practice of patriotic journalism whereas the *Daily News* pursues adversarial journalism, which holds the ZANU-PF government to account (Rusike, 1990; Saunders, 1999; Ranger, 2005; Chuma, 2008; Chibuwe, 2016; Maodza, 2024) especially when disasters natural or man-made, occur. Climate change is becoming a global security threat (Kesel & Sedlak, 2014) forcing governments to institute measures to combat its effects.

Debate on combating climate change has reached the United Nations Security Council amid concerns among member states that it threatened global security (Scheffran, 2009). Developing countries, especially in Africa and Asia, are more vulnerable to the negative effects of global warming due to their weak adaptive

mechanisms blamed on resource constraints and failure by the media to raise awareness. Former African Union Commission chairperson, Moussa Faki Mahamat described climate change as “an existential threat to Africa's communities, ecosystems and economy” (Source: African Union Climate Change & Resilient Development Strategy & Action Plan, 2022-2032). Europe considers climate change a “threat multiplier” exacerbating existing tensions and instabilities (Scheffran, 2009) as it promotes a scramble for resources owing to shortages occasioned by planetary warming. In Zimbabwe, President Emmerson Mnangagwa is on record describing climate change as a “health emergency” (Zinyuke, 2024) adding that there is, “No room for half measures in the climate change fight” (Bwititi, 2024). It is within this context that this study examines the state of climate change journalism at *The Herald* and *Daily News*. The mass media are vital disseminators of information especially during disasters. Zimbabwe has suffered climate change-induced disasters such as Cyclone Eline (2000); Cyclone Japhet (2003); and Cyclone Idai (2019). Cyclone Idai affected over three million people in Southern Africa (Mozambique, Malawi, & Zimbabwe) and killed thousands while destroying infrastructure running into billions of dollars (Mery Corps report, 2019).

Guided by Breed 1955's Sociology of News Production model and the political economy of the media theory, the overarching research question this study seeks to answer is: What is the state of climate change journalism in the Zimbabwean press? It also seeks an understanding of the challenges facing journalists involved in climate change reporting at *The Herald* and *Daily News*. Data for the study was gathered through in-depth interviews with purposively selected journalists at *The Herald* and *Daily News* to extract empirical evidence on the state of this specialized journalism genre in Zimbabwe. The threat posed by climate change on humanity must naturally attract interest from journalists from a news values perspective. This makes it important to examine the state of climate change journalism in the Zimbabwean press especially now when

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global warming is considered a threat to humanity globally. The media have the power to change opinions, habits, and attitudes (McQuail, 1983) and must help combat global warming by publishing news inspiring climate-proofing. The sociology of news production theory aids our understanding of news generation processes by zooming in on newsroom operations - how journalists gather and write stories, what newsroom factors influence how they report on issues while the political economy of the media model exposes the macro-factors shaping journalism. It draws from Marxian philosophy suggesting that owners of the means of production determine what to produce - and in the context of this study - how media ownership and control determine reportage of climate change. Thus, the sociology of news production model illuminates how journalists gather, compile and cause the publication of stories on climate change. The political economy theory shines a light on macropolitical-economic factors shaping and structuring climate journalism in the Zimbabwean press.

'Mediating' Climate Change in Africa

Scholars on the media and climate change concur that the press must play an active role in the fight against global warming (Cramer, 2008; Carval, 2010; Mare, 2011) with Evans (2015:164) insisting, "it seems only natural to expect the media ...to play a vital role in disseminating and interpreting information and helping to build adaptive capacity...". However, scholarship on climate journalism in Africa concurs that the African press is failing to treat climate change seriously (Cramer, 2008; Tabgo, 2010; Mare, 2011; Evans, 2015; Evans & Musvipwa, 2017; Pointer & Matsiko, 2023; Mbungu et al., 2024). It is within this context that the current study investigates the state of climate journalism in Zimbabwe with a special focus on two widely read daily newspapers, the state-controlled *The Herald* and the privately-owned *Daily News*. Whereas existing literature on the media and climate change in Zimbabwe (Evans, 2015; Mare, 2011; Evans & Musvipwa, 2017; Ndhlovu, 2021) either largely derived from content analysis or took "a jet plane view" (Chambwera, 2021) on the state of climate journalism in Africa, this study specifically engages journalists specializing in climate change to gain rich insights into the state of this genre. There is a paucity of scholarly work on the media and climate change in Zimbabwe with Pointer and Matsiko (2023:249) observing that "most studies about how African media cover climate change focus on South Africa and Nigeria...". This study, therefore, is relevant and significant as it reinforces existing discourses on the state of climate change journalism in Zimbabwe but draws from in-depth interviews with journalists specializing in climate journalism. Extant scholarship suggests that African media's coverage of climate change is sporadic, and event-driven (Cramer, 2008; Nwabueze et al., 2015, Okoliko, 2021; Pointer & Matsiko, 2023). They argue such editorial disposition ignores local voices and solutions. The media in Africa are reluctant to report on climate change and only increase coverage towards international summits on planetary warming or when their governments or Non-Governmental Organizations make pronouncements on the subject. Only the Ugandan and Kenyan media are less influenced by international events in their reportage of climate change (Nassanga et al., 2017) with the majority tracking global events.

Scholars also bemoan the tendency of the media in Africa to adopt frames that present climate change as insurmountable, catastrophic, and apocalyptic arguing this creates "a sense of hopelessness and

gloom" (Muasya et al., 2017:1) disempowering audiences (Shanahan, 2007) whom they are supposed to inspire mitigate and adapt and exhort the media on the continent to amplify reports promoting action against global warming. It has also been observed that the media in Africa give salience to politics, economics, entertainment, and sports as well as crime and poverty which are sellable to audiences (Moser & Dilling, 2004; Evans & Musvipwa, 2017) with Cramer (2008:16) arguing that "reporters are in the news business and not in the business of education or conservation". Further, extant scholarship bemoan the tendency of African media to rely on foreign media for stories about climate change on the continent, which they then fail to localize and contextualize (Mare, 2011; Evans, 2015) as also observed by Tabgo (2010:33) who noted that, "the bulk of the stories on climate change in the African media are usually taken straight from international wire services". The African media become echo chambers of foreign narratives and discourses on climate change and its impact on the continent (Gadzekpo, 2009).

While existing literature on climate change in Africa bemoans local media's reliance on global press for climate stories, episodic coverage, a tendency towards crisis climate journalism, promotion of the impact narrative in climate stories, and failure of editors to give salience to planetary warming, Mbungu et al. (2024) recommend major investment in climate journalism by frequently organizing capacity building workshops for journalists in Africa. This is important as in most instances journalists reporting on climate fail to simplify data for the ordinary person to understand. This explains why stories on climate change generated by African journalists are often jargon-laden (Mare, 2011) and not tailored to resonate with audiences' cultural and social values. The essence of the current study is in its attempt to seek nuanced understanding - through engagement with journalists reporting climate at *The Herald* and *Daily News* - of the current state of climate reporting in the Zimbabwean press to gather empirical evidence that enables marshalling of solutions aiding the press to play its role in combating global warming. Whereas scholars including Mare (2011) bemoan the dearth of investigative climate journalism, the current study responds to such concerns by seeking answers from the journalists themselves from the horse-mouth approach.

The Media and Climate Change in Zimbabwe

Through in-depth interviews with journalists directly involved in climate journalism, the current study seeks a nuanced understanding of the state of climate change journalism in Zimbabwe using *The Herald* and *Daily News* as case studies. The two newspapers are Zimbabwe's widely read dailies. The study captures the professional lived experiences of journalists specializing in climate change reporting. The central argument driving the study is that researchers can harvest important insights on the state of climate change journalism in Zimbabwe from journalists involved in the genre. Extant scholarship on the media and climate change in Zimbabwe (Mare, 2011; Evans & Musvipwa, 2017; Ndhlovu, 2021; Kutyaauripo et al., 2021) largely derives from content analysis - examining news articles generated by the media on climate change. Rarely are journalists engaged in climate change journalism interviewed to extract nuances on the challenges and prospects of this journalism genre in Zimbabwe. The current study attends to this omission. It is, however, critical to note that there is consensus among scholars that the media in Zimbabwe have failed to effectively report on climate

change despite the enormous threat it poses to humanity. In a study on the state of climate change journalism in southern Africa, Mare (2011) - whose research specifically focused on the *Sunday Mail* (Zimbabwe) and *Mail Guardian* (South Africa) - argues that press coverage of global warming-related matters is sporadic and lethargic with too much reliance on official sources while the reports are jargon-laden. This suggests a lack of commitment to climate change journalism by journalists in the case studied newspapers despite the “severity of the ongoing impact of climate change in Zimbabwe” (Evans, 2015:164). Mare (2011) also bemoans the lack of investigative stories on climate change partly attributing the situation to the “dearth of science journalists” in newsrooms. Equally, in a study focusing on how the media in southern Africa are mediating climate change, Evans and Musvipwa (2017) argue that international events on global warming cue local media narratives on climate change. They also note that climate change-related news articles are eclipsed by those on politics and the economy - again a suggestion that the media trivialize global warming. While acknowledging the immense contribution of these scholars (Mare, 2011; Evans & Musvipwa, 2017) it is significant to observe that their studies adopt a jet-plane view (Chambwera, 2021) to the study of the media and climate change. For example, Evans and Musvipwa (2017) case study several media organisations in southern Africa *The Standard*, *The Herald*, *Zimbabwe Broadcasting Corporation*, *South African Broadcasting Corporation*, *eNews Channel Africa* (ENCA, South Africa), *the Independent Online* (IOL, South Africa), *the Namibian & Mail & Guardian* - lacking incisive insights into the phenomenon as their research is too globalized. Secondly, Evans and Musvipwa (2017) subject stories on climate change generated by these news media to content analysis without due consideration for the experiences of the journalists who generated them. When they consulted them, they confessed to having interviewed “all the local in-house journalists who had stories published in the news media” without indication if the scribes specialized in climate change reporting, or if it was anyone who generated an article on the subject. This denied Evans and Musvipwa (2017) lucrative data from the rightful sources (climate change journalists), which could have generated priceless insights into the state of climate change journalism in southern Africa. Ndhlovu (2021) suffers the same limitation after subjecting to content analysis stories on climate change generated by columnists Jeffrey Gogo (*The Herald*) and Peter Makwanya (*NewsDay*). The pair's experiences are discounted. Ndhlovu (2021) could have gained rich insights into the forces shaping the pundits' construction of global warming from interviewing them. As a data-gathering method, content analysis is limited by its failure to account for human experiences - in this case insights from Gogo and Makwanya - to account for why they adopted certain news frames when reporting global warming. A similar challenge is evident in Kutyauro et al (2021) whose study examines the regularity of newspapers publishing articles on smart agriculture as a vehicle to arrest the negative effects of climate change and ensure food security.

Whereas there is consensus among scholars (Chaguta, 2006; Mare, 2011; Evans, 2011; Evans & Musvipwa, 2017; Ndhlovu, 2021) that the mainstream media fail to effectively report on climate change - an argument the current study supports - they struggle to account for the experiences of journalists reporting climate. We flag this grave methodological omission. Researchers can only extract informative insights from interviewing journalists directly involved

in the generation of texts and not restrict such research to content analysis. Failure to harvest such insights risks inconclusive conclusions. Equally, extant scholarship on climate change also tends to broaden its scope by ambitiously studying the state of climate journalism in “southern Africa”. Such broadness in scope risks a “jet-plane view” (Chambwera, 2021) short on incisive insights. The current study seeks a nuanced understanding of the state of climate change journalism from journalists specializing in this genre. Other researchers on climate change such as Evans (2015:164) examine how digital media can aid the fight against global warming in Zimbabwe and conclude that “new media is an excellent platform through which to promote climate change adaptation, disseminate information, build resilience capacity and enhance public comprehension”. They focus on how key nonmedia actors (Non-Governmental Organisations) are deploying digital media in climate monitoring and adaptation. The current study engages journalists specializing in climate change journalism to gain insights into the state of the journalism genre in the hope corrective action is taken.

Method

The study is qualitative and descriptive in its approach. It describes how journalists at *The Herald* and *Daily News* engage in climate journalism, explores the forces informing how they reported on planetary warnings, and assesses (interprets) the implications for this specialized journalism genre. The strength of a qualitative research approach is in its ability to capture the lived experiences of participants (Streubert & Carpenter, 1999; Polit & Beck, 2004). The researcher captures the lived newsroom experiences of purposively selected journalists at *The Herald* and *Daily News* involved in climate journalism. The study seeks informed insights into forces influencing climate journalism in the selected newspapers. It zooms in on actors promoting or demoting the practice of climate journalism at *The Herald* and *Daily News* while simultaneously examining how the newspaper reported on climate change. Considering “the severity of the ongoing impact of climate change in Zimbabwe, it seems only natural to expect the media... to play a vital role in disseminating and interpreting information...” (Evans, 2015:164). This research is a multiple case study - that focuses on two distinct newspapers, *The Herald* and *Daily News*, and comparatively assesses how they engage in climate journalism largely drawing from interviews with journalists specializing in this field. *The Herald* is a state-controlled newspaper reflecting government thinking on important matters (Rusike, 1990) like climate change whereas the *Daily News* is a privately-owned newspaper known for holding power (ZANU-PF) to account through its combative editorial disposition referred by scholars as oppositional/adversarial journalism (Saunders, 1999; Ranger, 2005; Maodza, 2024). Zainal (2007, 2007:1-2) notes that case studies enable researchers “to explore and investigate contemporary real-time phenomenon through detailed contextual analysis of a limited number of events or conditions and their relationship” and provide “an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context” (Yin, 1984:23). A comparative inquiry into how *The Herald* and *Daily News* report on climate change aids in exposing similarities and dissimilarities in their editorial positions as they regard to global warming enabling researchers have a broad picture on the challenges journalists at the two newspapers encounter when reporting on planetary warming and how they

overcome them. Noting that case studies fall into various categories - ranging from descriptive, exploratory, interpretive, and explanatory to evaluative approaches - the study uses descriptive and explanatory research designs. A descriptive design attempts to answer what, when, and how of a research problem through thick description. A descriptive design pictures a situation but fails to account for why a phenomenon may have occurred in a certain way (Punch, 2005). This explains why the study also deploys the explanatory design as it seeks to understand why a phenomenon unfolded in a certain way (Grey, 2014). Thus, the explanatory research design attempts to answer the “how” and why questions. In the context of this study, the explanatory design enables the researcher to account for the editorial behaviour disposition of journalists engaged in climate journalism at *The Herald* and *Daily News*. Making up this study's population are four journalists specialising in climate journalism at *The Herald* and *Daily News* - purposively selected for interviews strictly on that basis. Researchers saw no value in interviewing journalists specialising in other beats such as sports, entertainment and politics. Purposive sampling directs a researcher to information rich sources (Patton, 2002). For demonstrative purposes - to reinforce data emerging from interviews - a total of 14 stories (seven from each newspaper) were subjected to content analysis. Although data for this study largely draws from interviews with journalists specialising in climate reporting, naturally there was a need to analyse the stories and enable in-depth interviewing of journalists - they had to account for the nature of stories they generated. The study is confined to 2024 when President Mnangagwa and his administration heightened rhetoric on the need for a national response to negative effects of climate change. It is in this context that the study locates the media's editorial behaviour insofar as it pertains to climate change.

Results

Journalists' Comprehension of Climate Change

Interviews with journalists reporting on climate confirmed their appreciation of global warming and its implications on humanity. A senior journalist at *The Herald* identified for this study as Participant A, defined planetary warming as “the variation of the weather that has been happening over the past years”. They were specific that whereas many people confuse climate change with weather patterns, the two were different noting that, “climate change is over a period of time whereas weather is a daily variation”. The journalist has reported on agriculture and climate change for nearly two decades. While there is no desk specifically focusing on climate change at *The Herald*, the genre is incorporated within the agriculture portfolio. This derives from the editor's understanding of agriculture and climate as intertwined. The Herald agriculture desk was established after Robert Mugabe led ZANU-PF instituted a controversial fast-track land reform program. White-owned commercial farms were compulsorily appropriated without compensation with Mugabe adamant his administration was addressing land ownership imbalances - white commercial farmers owned more land than blacks, who by population constitute the majority in Zimbabwe. To support the ZANU-PF ideology, *The Herald* invested in agriculture journalism as a means to ensure the new black farmer is fed agriculture-related information aiding productivity in the process. It is within this context that this desk (agriculture) was established and covers climate change related issues as part of its broader mandate. An interview with another senior journalist at *The Herald*

specializing in reporting science, who for purposes of the study is identified as Participant B, also confirmed reporters at the state-controlled newspaper comprehend climate journalism. This raises questions as to why the newspaper seemingly fails to treat global warming seriously regardless of its threat. When asked, what is climate journalism? Participant B responded, “It is “quite broad” as it “ranges from reporting the causes of climate change, the impact and copying mechanisms employed by communities and also policy related issues as they relate to global warming”. The journalist's definition aligns with Schafer and Painter's (2020) view that climate journalism is the gathering, evaluation, selection, and presentation of information on climate change inclusive of its causes and impact to enable mitigation and adaptation by communities. Participant B indicated they were trained in climate journalism after attending several international workshops on reporting science.

I was trained in climate change reporting. It is from such international workshops and conferences that I gained knowledge of reporting science. These workshops were organized by scientists from countries including the United States of America, the United Kingdom, and Australia. This enabled me to process complex scientific information into simple but interesting climate stories for the benefit of audiences (interview with researcher, Harare, 18 December 2024).

It is significant to note that Participant B received training in science communication courtesy of well-wishers within civil society as the employer (*The Herald*) “had no resources” to fund the journalist's foreign workshops on climate journalism and science reporting even though it sponsored reporters covering politics and sports to attend global events. This implies that management at *The Herald* is reluctant to invest in climate journalism despite the adverse effects of global warming in Zimbabwe, which has either experienced severe droughts or flooding at a cost to life and infrastructure. Throughout the interview with the researcher, Participant B insisted they were driven by a “passion for climate journalism” hence “outsourcing” funding to attend a science communication workshop abroad. *The Herald's* reluctance to invest in climate journalism is also confirmed by Participant A.

“At times there is a workshop on climate change in Zambia and you have been invited by organisers but the company has no resources for your travel. They (management) cite financial constraints. You then miss such important workshops unless organisers (of the event) fund your travel and subsistence for the duration of the event” (Interview with researcher, Harare, 18 December 2024).

Zimbabwe is 491 km from Zambia (Harare to Lusaka by road), and this demonstrates a lack of commitment by the newspaper to invest in climate journalism. Journalists end up funded by civil society engaged in climate change activism to attend such conferences. There is a risk of capture by civil society whose narratives journalists then promote when writing stories on climate change. It is equally revealing that whereas Participant B is well grounded in climate journalism owing to outside newsroom training, Participant A has challenges processing information on climate change due to lack of training.

For example, I would struggle to interpret what El Nino or La Nina for the ordinary audience, yet we needed to simplify these terms for them. I faced some challenges with terms used by scientists related to climate change (Interview with Participant A, Harare, 18 December 2024).

Having surmised that climate journalists at *The Herald* appreciate the concept of global warming and climate journalism, the researcher sought answers on how they gather and process information on climate change - again by interviewing them. The next section highlights news sourcing challenges journalists face when reporting climate.

The Political Economy of Climate Change Journalism in Zimbabwe: Industrial Capture, Officialdom, and the Raw "Imports"

From interviews with journalists, the researcher identified several factors affecting the practice of climate journalism at *The Herald*, which may account for the newspaper's struggle to mobilize efforts at mitigation and adaptation. These include alleged "capture" of the newspaper by industrialists (business), dependency on unreliable government sources (officialization), and deriving climate stories from foreign news agencies without contextualizing them.

Capture by Industrialists and the Consequences on Climate Journalism

Industrialists, committing environmental offences, have allegedly captured the press riding on their financial muscle as major advertisers. Zimbabwe's economy is struggling and only a few international companies remain - and these have become untouchable. This was revealed by Participant B and supported by other journalists interviewed by the researcher.

As a journalist reporting climate change and its impact on communities, I am unable even with evidence - to generate stories that expose these big companies in Zimbabwe (names withheld) discharging raw industrial waste and raw sewer into water sources destabilizing aqua life and putting the lives of Harare residents at risk. They discharge raw industrial waste into Mukuvisi River which flows into Lake Chivero. The moment you attempt to write an investigative story exposing such industrialists, they react by withdrawing their adverts from the newspaper. This is "industrial" capitalism. Advertising is a major source of revenue for the newspaper, and we cannot offend the industrialists. Ultimately management capitulates and the story is killed. Meanwhile, the industrialists continue dumping waste into water sources (Participant B, interview with researcher, 18 December 2024, Harare).

There was a disaster at Lake Chivero in December 2024 when wild animals died after consuming heavily polluted water. This saw Harare City - which draws water for human consumption from Lake Chivero - stopping water supplies for days as the Zimbabwe Parks and Wildlife Management Authority and the University of Zimbabwe investigated the matter. However, the Zimbabwe Parks and Wildlife Authority - a government entity - blamed the animal and fish deaths on cyanobacteria (Source: *The Herald*, 25 December 2024). In January 2025, Zimbabwe again witnessed the death of wildlife and fish in Masvingo province, which the Environmental Management Agency (EMA) - after investigations -blamed on cyanide and sodium hydroxide spillage from gold mining activities by Chinese companies. Interestingly, *The Herald* failed to report on this scandal, a development which to some extent proved true Participant B's claims of press capture by industrialists.

This is affecting all the newspapers. It has reached alarming levels. No single newspaper will report on it. Industrialists have

captured the media. You cannot name and shame polluters and enable responsible authorities to act on it (Interview with Participant B, 18 December 2024, Harare).

The claim (media capture by industry) was also confirmed by Participant B although they were reluctant to give more details beyond, "It's known here that we must not offend our major advertisers such as (names withheld) even though they are messing the environment". The same situation haunts the *Daily News* with a journalist interviewed by the researcher, identified as Participant C, attributing the sporadic coverage of climate change-related news to the political economy of the media in Zimbabwe. Participant C claimed coverage of some sensitive climate stories, "will expose the dire situation on the ground, which authorities fear might cause anarchy. The one who pays the piper dictates the tune".

Climate Change News Sourcing Dilemma - Officialdom, "Shy" Experts, and the Unprocessed Imports

Findings deriving from interviews with journalists involved in climate journalism suggest the priming of "government voices" especially at the state-controlled *The Herald* and over-reliance on foreign media for climate stories (the unprocessed imports). Participants A and B claimed that by *The Herald* being a state-controlled newspaper, journalists involved in climate reporting are naturally mandated to source stories from the government. They indicated in some instances they are given false information, which they do not contest but process and report.

An example is the Ministry of Lands, Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development which tends to inflate grain harvest statistics every year. It seems they do it for political purposes (propaganda) but then as a journalist for *The Herald*, I cannot challenge such information. We simply write a story out of it. You must comply with the information given even if you doubt it (Interview with Participant B, 18 December 2024, Harare).

Participant B raised the same concerns saying it becomes even more difficult when non-government actors carry out independent assessments whose results defy statistics given by the government adding, "We simply comply with information released to us by government even if we strongly doubt it" (Interview with Participant A, 18 December 2024). This suggests that journalists involved in climate journalism at *The Herald* occasionally regurgitate without verifying information released by the government, especially on measures taken to mitigate global warming. This explains why Participants A and B indicated they simply reproduce what is given to them (grain output statistics) even when the figures may be inflated. How this is climate change related - owing to global warming government encourages the growing of small grains (traditional African grains like sorghum) as part of a climate adaptation strategy that ensures food security at the household level. From the interviews, journalists claim the government inflates yields for propaganda purposes. This distorts news on climate change mitigation and adaptation owing to the deliberate manipulation of information by the arms of the state. Participant A also claimed *The Herald* mainly gives priority to climate change especially when government officials "have spoken about it". They indicated stories are then framed in a manner that emphasizes the success of mitigatory measures taken by the ZANU-PF government. Such an approach ignores the voices of ordinary citizens who bear the brunt of climate change. Participant A revealed that salience was always given "to stories projecting measures the government was adopting

to climate-proof Zimbabweans from the negative effects of global warming". According to the journalist (Participant A), this explained why *The Herald* routinely published stories about the government-sponsored *Pfumvudza/Intwasa* program deriving from pronouncements by government officials. *Pfumvunza/Intwasa* is a government-led initiative that promotes climate resilient agriculture. It is conservation agriculture which advocates maintenance of permanent soil cover and discourages mechanized farming. Participant A also claimed, "in most instances, pressure came from the ministry of agriculture demanding that we publicize *Pfumvunza/Intwasa* and create awareness thereby ensuring the ordinary farmer knows the mitigatory measures available for them" and climate proof. In the process, ordinary voices were drowned especially as *The Herald* could not fund outside newsroom trips for their voices owing to resource constraints (Participant A).

What also emerged from the interviews with climate journalists is the reluctance of climate experts to engage the media on issues related to global warming, limiting diversity in news sources. Participant B revealed that while they always seek comments from climate change experts at local universities, the majority are reluctant but singled out a retired University of Zimbabwe lecturer, "who fearlessly shared his thought on climate change" adding that, "the majority do not want to offend government" hence the reluctance. Participant B bemoaned the status quo stating that, "we should have material written by intellectuals which seeks to inform national leaders even about policy issues around climate change. These are our thought leaders". Participant C (*Daily News* journalist) raised the same point noting that, "There is a shortage of experts who want to comment on climate issues. The few that are there do not want to comment maybe for fear of victimization". The journalist's remark suggests that climate change is a politically sensitive subject, which some experts avoid discussing with the media at all costs. This compounds the situation as climate journalists require experts to process complex climate issues (Mare, 2011).

It also emerged from the interviews with climate journalists that global media shape local media narratives on climate change. There is a tendency by editors to harvest stories online generated overseas and plant them on newspaper pages, a position also confirmed by the *Daily News* reporter (Participant C) when they revealed, "Mostly we develop our stories based on stuff we find on the internet, but the challenge is the majority of it is from developed countries". Participant B (Senior Journalist at *The Herald*) partly blamed the situation on a lack of passion in the newsroom for climate change, which other journalists believe is not lucrative enough for their sustenance. Participant B alleged, "The issue is that it is not so attractive. *Hakuna bribes* (there are no bribes). You cannot demand a bribe from professionals like professors who are also struggling due to poor remuneration." Owing to a struggling economy in Zimbabwe, academicians are poorly paid. Participant B also indicated that young journalists feel that climate change does not bring them the spotlight like other beats such as entertainment, sports, business, and politics where they have an opportunity "to rub shoulders with celebrities".

This at times starves newspaper stories on climate change, which may be due to lack of competition among journalists to write climate change-related scoops (exposés). In some instances, journalists blame the government "for not doing much to mitigate the effects of drought, for example by building resilience among affected communities" (Participant C, *Daily News* journalist). This

standpoint suggests that climate-related news must emanate from actions taken by the government to build resilience. It discounts ordinary people's voices on measures they take at the community level to adapt to climate change hazards while exposing the extent journalists fail to realize the media's role in promoting awareness.

It further emerged from the interviews with climate journalists that editors do not treat climate change-related stories seriously. This accounts for why they are eclipsed by stories from portfolios such as politics, sports, entertainment, and business. The status quo compounds the situation as journalists specializing in climate change are demotivated when their articles are denied saliency or not even published. Further, unlike other newsroom portfolios that have a clear structure, the climate beat runs "haphazardly" with a skeletal structure comprising a journalist or two as observed by Participant A, "you will find one or two journalists specializing or assigned to climate/agriculture" and "when they are absent, "students are assigned the portfolio". The same happens at *Daily News* with Participant D indicating, "we only have one reporter who is interested in climate journalism in Bulawayo and another in Harare, who writes a lot about global warming".

The Herald's Climate Journalism is Influenced by Global Events

As illustrated in Figure 1 below, *The Herald* gave sufficient attention to climate change related news during the period under study. The state-controlled newspapers published 32 articles between October and December 2024. On the surface, this projects *The Herald* as proactive in climate change journalism. A closer analysis, however, confirms an argument by existing scholarship (Osindo, 2014; Nwabueze & Egbra, 2016; Kakonge, 2020; Pointer & Matsiko, 2023) that the African media's reportage of global warming is strongly influenced by global events. The press tracks global events. *The Herald* only upped its reportage of climate change toward, during and soon after the 29th Conference of Parties (COP29) held in Baku, Azerbaijan, attended by President Emmerson Mnangagwa. The story became Mnangagwa. *The Herald*, as shown in Figure 1 below, published 14 climate change related stories between October 31 and November 14, 2024. This translates to a climate story every day for 14 consecutive days. It is, however, crucial to note that the stories were largely centred on Mnangagwa than climate change. It is also significant to indicate that the stories were generated by journalists (Kuda Bwititi & Wallace Ruzvidzo), who by designation are political reporters not attached to the climate portfolio in the newsroom. This arises from the fact that journalists specializing in climate journalism are not presidential correspondents and as a result get sidelined from such important summits as COP29. Presidential correspondents, in the context of *The Herald* operations, are journalists assigned to report on all local or foreign activities involving the president. Whereas Ruzvidzo and Bwititi had the opportunity in Baku to engage global climate experts, it is clear from the stories they generated as shown in Figure 1, that they focused only on Mnangagwa's pronouncements - the officialdom syndrome. It is also interesting to observe that all stories involving the president were placed on front page giving them salience while the rest were hidden on inside pages. Equally important to note, as also shown in Figure 1 below, all the stories are derived from events hosted by the government. Government, therefore, shaped and structured *The Herald's* narratives on climate change. It is also clear from the table below that *The Herald* seemed to politicize and propagandize the

ZANU-PF government's mitigatory programmes such as *Pfumvunza/Intwasa*. *Pfumvunza/Intwasa* - an ancient conservation method - is projected as a government groundbreaking innovation towards climate adaptation. Under the scheme, President

Mnangagwa provides inputs to villagers every farming season, and this accounts for The Herald's celebratory approach when reporting about *Pfumvunza/Intwasa*.

Figure 1

Climate Change-related Stories Published by The Herald during the Period under Study

Date	The Herald Stories	Sources/Voices	Author	Page
21/10/2024	<i>Pfumvudza, Zunde raMambo</i> : Pioneering food security in Zimbabwe	Event derived	Jimmy Murwira	Inside Pages
22/10/2024	Farmers start collecting <i>Pfumvudza</i> inputs	Event derived	Herald Reporters	Inside Pages
29/10/2024	Tavengwa launches 2024/25 <i>Pfumvunza/Intwasa</i> scheme in Epworth	Government sourced and Event Derived	Trust Freddy	Inside Pages
30/10/2024	200K Harare residents to benefit from <i>Pfumvudza</i> scheme	Event derived	Trust Freddy	Inside Pages
31/10/2024	Over eight million <i>Pfumvudza</i> plots ready for planting	Government sourced	Precious Manomano	Inside Pages
22/11/2024	Beneficiaries applaud timely distribution of <i>Pfumvudza</i> inputs	Event derived	Victor Maposa	Inside Pages
24/11/2024	First Lady launches <i>Pfumvudza</i> programme in Mt Darwin	Event derived	Tendai Rupapa	Inside Pages
24/11/2024	<i>Pfumvudza</i> distribution in full swing	Event derived	Herald Reporters	Inside Pages
31/10/2024 (event derived)	Climate change a health emergency: President Rumbidzai Zinyuke	President speech Front Page		
01/11/2024 (event based)	Embrace <i>Pfumvudza/Intwasa</i> , Farmers urged Fungai Lupande	Government sourced Inside Pages		
10/11/2024	52000 households in Bindura to benefit from <i>Pfumvunza</i> inputs	Government (event based)	Fungai Lupande	Inside Pages
10/11/2024	President arrives in Azerbaijan for climate change summit	Government sourced and event derived	Kuda Bwititi	Front Page
11/11/2024	Pivoting on Banana winemaking to beat climate change	Expert sourced	Sifelani Tsiko	Inside Pages
11/11/2024	Zim commits to green building in light of climate change	Government sourced	Herald correspondent	Inside Pages
11/11/2024	Research institute tackle climate change	Event derived	Precious Manomano	Inside Pages
11/11/2024	Global climate indaba: what at stake?	Opinionated article	Kuda Bwititi	Inside Pages
11/11/2024	Respect Developing Nations' view: President	President Speech Event derived	Kuda Bwititi	Front page
14/11/2024	President back home from Azerbaijan	Event derived	Wallace Ruzvidzo	Front Page
12/11/2024	Climate Smart agriculture pays off	President speech	Kuda Bwititi	Front page
12/11/2024	President urges Diaspora to share innovative ideas	President Speech (Event derived)	Kuda Bwititi	Front Page
12/11/2024	Zimbabwe unwavering in commitment to fight climate change - Sadc Chair	President Speech Event derived	Kuda Bwititi	Front Page
13/11/2024	No room for half measures in climate change fight	President speech (Event derived)	Kuda Bwititi	Front Page
14/11/2024	President ends Azerbaijan visit	Event derived	Wallace Ruzvidzo	Front Page
14/11/2024	Fighting climate change requires huge investment	Editor's comment	Editor	Centre Page
15/11/2024	Funding key to climate change fight: President	President speech at COP29 (Event derived)	Kuda Bwititi	Front Page
23/11/2024	Climate change risking lives of pregnant women	Non-Governmental Organisation (Event derived)	Fungai Lupande Bindura Bureau	Inside Page
26/11/2024	Farmers urged to take insurance in the face of climate change	Event derived	Herald Reporter	Inside Page
03/12/2024	Over 80 percent <i>Pfumvudza</i> inputs distributed	Government sourced	Precious Manomano	Inside Pages
04/12/2024	Victoria Falls feels impact of climate change	Reporter generated picture and caption	Wilson Kakurira	Inside Page
04/12/2024	Call for SADC to harmonise climate change fight	Event derived	Tanyaradzwa Kutaura	Inside Page
10/12/2024	Heat wave exposes climate change vulnerability	Opinionated article	Desmond Manatsa (Correspondent)	Inside Page
17/12/2024	Climate change goes gear up	Opinionated article	Willard Duri (Correspondent)	Inside Page

The Daily News's "Officialization" of Climate Change Reports

As illustrated in the table below (Figure 2), the *Daily News* generated only seven climate change related in the period under study (October to December 2024) and 13 articles in 10 months, as again shown. This suggests lack of commitment to climate journalism. The newspaper relied heavily on official sources for its stories with seven out of the 13 published articles derived from government sources. The newspaper became an echo chamber for government narratives on climate change while sidelining ordinary people who bear the brunt of negative effects of global warming. Alternatively, the *Daily News* - as a privately-owned newspaper known for its pursuit of justice through its practice of oppositional or adversarial journalism (Ranger, 2005) became an extension of the state-controlled media such as *The Herald* by regurgitating government's position on climate change. The newspaper also imported stories from online sources as shown in the table - "Women leading battle against climate change" was harvested from Inter Press News Agency (IPS).

IPS is an international communication institution, which claims to cater to voices of the South and civil society on matters related to development, human rights, and the environment. The *Daily News* also imported from the British Broadcasting Corporation an article titled, "Climate change is turbo-charging Somalia's problems...but there is still hope" written by Justin Rowlatt. They failed to contextualise the story and make it relevant to local audiences. This reinforces concerns by existing scholarship (Gadzekpo, 2009; Tagbo, 2010; Mare, 2011; Evans and Musvipwa, 2017) who argue that by failing to localise and contextualise climate stories, local media become amplifiers of messages from others. The fact that none of the climate stories generated by *Daily News* earned front page speaks volumes about how the newspaper regards global warming. As shown in Figure 2, the stories were hidden inside pages denying them salience. In print media, a front page is reserved for stories editors consider more newsworthy while those deemed not so important are hidden inside pages. Thus, a story is more visible and therefore important when on the front page (Siegel, 2022).

Figure 2

Stories on Climate Change Published by the Daily News

Date	Daily News	Sources/Voice	Author	Page
03/3/2024	Disaster at the intersection of cholera and climate change	Online (Global Press Journal)	Staff Writer	Inside Pages
02/04/2024	Government calls for inclusive climate action	Government	Yvonne Ncube	Inside Pages
08/08/2024	Align industrial practices with climate change principles	Government	Hazel Marimbiza	Inside pages
11/08/2024	Coltart Challenges youth on climate change	Bulawayo Mayor (event derived)	Hazel Marimbiza	Inside Pages
23/08/2024	Climate change needs gender-sensitive policies	Government	Hazel Marimbiza	Inside Pages
18/09/2024	Climate change is turbo-charging Somalia's problems...but there is still hope	Sourced from BBC	BBC Climate editor, Justin Rowlatt	Inside Pages
29/10/2024	Pfumvunza/Intwasa inputs in short supply	Government	Stella Madzivanyika	Inside Pages
31/10/2024	Mobilise Resources against climate change	President (COP29 speech)	Shamaine Chirimujiri	Inside Pages
01/11/2024	Climate change affecting kids mental health - Unicef	Unicef	Hazel Marimbiza	Inside Pages
06/11/2024	Faith leaders unite against climate change	Press conference by churches	Shamaine Chirimujiri	Inside Pages
15/11/2024	Pfumvudza inputs distribution surpasses 50 percent	Government	Hazel Marimbiza	Inside Pages
30/11/2024	Indigenous forests are key in fighting climate change	Government	Staff writer	Inside Pages
29/12/2024	Women leading battle against climate change	Story taken online (IPS)	Staff writer	Inside Pages

Discussion and Conclusion

Findings from interviews with journalists at *The Herald* and *Daily News* suggest that Zimbabwe's major daily newspapers do not treat climate change seriously. With the *Daily News*, this lack of seriousness is shown by the few stories that privately owned newspapers published during the period under review. The newspaper only published 13 stories on climate change in 2024. Of the 13, two were harvested online from global media houses. "Women leading battle against climate change" (29 December 2024) was taken from Inter Press News Agency (IPS) while "Climate change is turbo-charging Somalia's problems...but there is still hope" (18 September 2024) was sourced from the British

Broadcasting Corporation (BBC). The stories lack context after the newspaper failed to localise them and ensure they are relevant to Zimbabweans. This confirms arguments by scholars (Gadzekpo, 2009; Tagbo, 2010; Mare, 2011; Evans & Musvipwa, 2017) that African media's narratives on climate change are influenced by global media and local press become echo chambers of discourses far removed from their contexts. In that context, the African media fail to effectively aid the fight against climate change as the messages they disseminate do not resonate with the reality on the ground. It is equally informative to note that of the 13 stories that were published by *Daily News* on climate change, none made it to the front page. While this might sound mundane, it is important to note that in newspaper production the placement of an article on the front

page reflects the seriousness or lack of it a newspaper considers an issue (Siegel, 2022). Serious issues earn the front page whereas trivial matters are hidden on inside pages. From this perspective, it is arguable therefore that *Daily News* does not consider climate change a serious issue worth giving saliency through placement on the front page.

The same challenge manifests at *The Herald* but is rather different. The state-controlled newspaper only places front page climate change stories involving the president and or a senior government official. The story is then modelled around the source in such a manner that fails to prioritise the subject (climate change). Figure 1 illustrates this point. Of the 32 stories published by *The Herald* during the period, the eight that earned the front page derived from President Mnangagwa as the source and the president became the story and NOT climate change. The tendency of *The Herald* to “officialise” climate change disregards the voices of ordinary people limiting their contribution to climate change proofing. Interestingly, the newspaper mainly quotes ordinary people's voices only when it wants them to rubber stamp government sponsored programmes like *Pfumvunza/Intwasa*. This is evident in the event-based stories, “Farmers start collecting *Pfumvudza* inputs” (22 October 2024), “Beneficiaries applaud timely distribution of *Pfumvudza* inputs” (22 November 2024), and First Lady Launches *Pfumvudza* in Mt Darwin”. These stories do not go beyond celebrating government's sponsored *Pfumvudza/Intwasa* a revolutionary climate-proofing programme that will guarantee food security at the household level. It is also equally important to note that most of the stories published by *The Herald* and *Daily News* were event-based and derived from events organised by government. Journalists failed to beyond speech reporting and single sourcing of stories. Of the 32 stories published by *The Herald* 22 were event-driven with journalists failing to expand them beyond the speech while nine of *Daily News*' 13 stories also derived from events either by government or non-government organisations. This confirms observations by scholars (Mare, 2011; Osindo, 2014; Nwabueze, 2016; Kakonge, 2020) that climate change journalism in Africa is event-driven. Journalists at *The Herald* are naturally forced to derive stories from government activities by the newspaper's political economy - government-controlled. *Daily News* is better placed to independently source stories as it suffers no direct state interference in its editorial operations. However, findings from interviews and assessment of stories published by *Daily News* suggest that the newspaper failed to leverage this advantage when it equally relied on government sources for stories on climate change literacy becoming an extension of *The Herald* in its narratives.

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